

Secondary School Teachers' Perceptions: Integrating the National Consolidated Mathematics Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District, Guyana

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Abstract

This study delves into secondary school teachers' perceptions regarding the integration of the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of Region 6, Guyana. Utilising a quantitative approach, data was gathered from 30 teachers across four secondary schools using stratified sampling. The findings suggest an overall positive reception of the curriculum among teachers, with a consensus on its relevance to students' lives and its effectiveness in providing learning opportunities and enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, nuanced considerations have emerged, particularly regarding concerns about the curriculum's rigidity, abstractness, and gender-based variations in teachers' perceptions. Statistical analyses, including t-tests and ANOVA tests, revealed significant differences in perceptions between male and female teachers and the influence of teachers' years of experience on their perceptions. These findings underscore the importance of tailored approaches to curriculum implementation, collaborative efforts among stakeholders, and providing adequate support and professional development opportunities for educators. Addressing these considerations is crucial for enhancing the quality and effectiveness of mathematics education in the region, ultimately benefiting both students and teachers.

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Introduction

The primary pillar of education in our society shapes the futures of individuals and society as a whole. In recent years, there has been an increasing emphasis on curricular reform to ensure that students are adequately equipped to face the challenges of the 21st century (Reis, 2018). Adopting the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in Secondary Schools is crucial for educational reform in East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana. The national Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum is the result of a deliberate attempt to provide students with a thorough and coherent Mathematics Education that covers key ideas and skills at every grade level (Jules, 2020).

Improved Mathematics Education outcomes in East Berbice Corentyne and, consequently, improved student preparation for postsecondary education and the workforce depend on the successful integration of this curriculum. Although curriculum modifications are frequently well-intentioned, their effectiveness depends on how field educators view and carry them out. Secondary school teachers are crucial to this process, as it is up to them to convert curricular materials into useful classroom instruction (Jules, 2020; Bhainie, 2021). To evaluate the reform's success and spot potential obstacles and areas for development, it is essential to understand their perceptions and experiences with integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum.

Despite the growing understanding of the significance of integrating the mathematics curriculum into secondary education, empirical research into secondary school teachers' views of integrating the mathematics consolidated curriculum in East Berbice Corentyne is lacking. This study aims to close this gap by examining instructors' attitudes and views of the integration process. For the curriculum to be implemented successfully and for students to succeed in mathematics, it is essential to comprehend these viewpoints. Hence the study was guided by the following questions:

1. What are Secondary School Teachers' perceptions of integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?
2. Is there a relationship between Secondary School Teachers' gender and their perception of integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?
3. Is there a relationship between Secondary School Teachers' years of experience and their perception of integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?

By addressing these questions, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the implementation of the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in secondary schools and contribute to the ongoing efforts for educational reform in the Lower Corentyne District of Guyana.

Materials and Methods

Sampling and Participants

The population for this study consisted of 50 mathematics teachers from 4 secondary schools in the Lower Corentyne District. The researchers used stratified random sampling to select a representative sample of 30 teachers (60% of the population), categorised by gender into 15 males and 15 females.

Instrumentation

The researchers utilised a self-designed questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was carefully constructed based on the research problem and literature review and included two sections: Section A for demographic information and Section B with 15 close-ended questions using a 4-point Likert scale. To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of four experts, including the researcher's supervisor, a content specialist, a language specialist, and a measurement and evaluation specialist. Their feedback was incorporated to refine the instrument before pilot testing. The reliability of the questionnaire was established through a pilot study with mathematics teachers outside the target population. The internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.80, indicating high reliability.

Data Collection and Analysis

The electronic questionnaires were administered to the sample teachers using the Google Forms platform. Participants who lacked access to electronic devices were accommodated where a printed questionnaire was delivered to them via the principal to maintain anonymity. Data was collected over 72 hours, recorded on suitable tables in Microsoft Excel and then analysed using SPSS software.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers obtained permission from the Chief Education Officer of Guyana and school administrators. Participants were assured of confidentiality, and their participation was voluntary. A cover letter accompanied the questionnaire to emphasise the importance of the study and the rationale for their participation.

Results

The results of this study are presented by the research question.

Research Question 1

What are secondary school teachers' perceptions on integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?

Table 1. Descriptive Analysis of Mathematics Teachers' Perception of Integrating the Consolidated Mathematics Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne – Guyana

<i>Items</i>	Mean	Inference	Standard Error	Standard Deviation	Sample Variance
1. The consolidated mathematics curriculum is more relevant to students' lives.	2.867	Agree	0.115	0.629	0.395
2. The consolidated mathematics curriculum offers students better learning opportunities.	2.900	Agree	0.121	0.662	0.438
3. The consolidated mathematics curriculum employs student-centred teaching techniques.	2.867	Agree	0.124	0.681	0.464
4. The consolidated mathematics curriculum provides teaching approaches that improve students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	2.933	Agree	0.117	0.640	0.409
5. The consolidated mathematics curriculum promotes project-based learning.	2.767	Agree	0.114	0.626	0.392
6. The consolidated mathematics curriculum is easy to follow while teaching.	3.000	Agree	0.144	0.788	0.621
7. The consolidated mathematics curriculum is designed to meet the demands of the learners.	2.767	Agree	0.124	0.679	0.461
8. The consolidated mathematics curriculum connects significant math concepts with other disciplines.	2.900	Agree	0.111	0.607	0.369
9. The consolidated mathematics curriculum helps students collaborate in problem-solving.	2.967	Agree	0.112	0.615	0.378
10. The consolidated mathematics curriculum is rigid and abstract.	2.767	Agree	0.124	0.679	0.461
11. The consolidated mathematics curriculum is based on a clear theoretical framework.	2.933	Agree	0.095	0.521	0.271
12. I am prepared to teach the consolidated mathematics curriculum.	3.033	Agree	0.131	0.718	0.516
13. My views as a stakeholder were factored into the design of the consolidated mathematics curriculum.	2.533	Agree	0.115	0.629	0.395
14. There are sufficient professional development outreach programs to provide teachers with the appropriate training to implement the consolidated mathematics curriculum.	2.567	Agree	0.124	0.679	0.461
15. There are sufficient materials to implement the mathematics consolidated curriculum.	2.700	Agree	0.145	0.794	0.631

Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of secondary school teachers' perceptions regarding integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana. A systematic analysis of various items, encompassing aspects such as relevance to students' lives, learning opportunities, teaching techniques, and resource availability, has revealed valuable insights into teachers' perspectives. The findings suggest a predominantly positive reception of the curriculum among teachers, albeit with nuanced considerations across different dimensions.

One key aspect highlighted by the data is the perceived relevance of the consolidated mathematics curriculum to students' lives. Teachers generally agreed that the curriculum resonates with the experiences and needs of students, indicating a potential alignment with real-world applications (Item 1: Mean = 2.867). This aspect is crucial

as it underscores the importance of contextualised learning experiences in fostering student engagement and understanding.

Furthermore, teachers expressed favourable views regarding the effectiveness of the curriculum in providing learning opportunities and enhancing students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Incorporating student-centred teaching techniques is also acknowledged, reflecting a pedagogical approach prioritising active engagement and participation (Item 4: Mean = 2.933). However, concerns regarding the rigidity and abstractness of the curriculum emerged, suggesting areas where further refinement or adaptation may be warranted to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences (Item 10: Mean = 2.767).

Moreover, while teachers generally perceived themselves as prepared to teach the consolidated mathematics curriculum (Item 12: Mean = 3.033), there are notable considerations regarding stakeholder involvement in the curriculum design process and the availability of adequate professional development programs and materials (Item 13: Mean = 2.533; Item 14: Mean = 2.567). These findings underscore the importance of collaborative and continuous efforts in curriculum development and teacher training initiatives, ensuring educators have the necessary support and resources to implement the curriculum effectively.

While the overall reception appears positive, nuanced considerations and improvement areas warrant attention from policymakers, curriculum developers, and education stakeholders. By addressing these concerns and leveraging the identified strengths, efforts can be made to enhance the quality and effectiveness of mathematics education in the region, ultimately benefiting students and educators alike.

Research Question 2

Is there a relationship between secondary school teacher' gender and their perception of the integration of the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?

Hypothesis Testing

H_0 – There is no relationship between secondary school teacher' gender and their perception of integrating the Consolidated Mathematics Curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana

Table 2.T-Test Showing the Relationship between the Variables

t-Test		
	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	6.5	2.833
Variance	0.259	0.242
Observations	30	30
Pooled Variance	0.250	
Hypothesised Mean Difference	0	
Df	58	
t Stat	28.382	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.23475E-36	
t Critical one-tail	1.672	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.04695E-35	
t Critical two-tail	2.002	

The t-test results (Table 2) indicate a significant difference in the perceptions of integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum between male and female secondary school teachers in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana. The mean perception score for male teachers is notably higher at 6.5 compared to female teachers, whose mean perception score is 2.833. This disparity suggests a potential gender-related discrepancy in how teachers perceive the effectiveness or adequacy of curriculum integration. The observed variance within each group is relatively similar, indicating consistent responses among male and female teachers.

The calculated t-value of 28.382 far exceeds the critical t-values for both one-tail and two-tail tests, indicating a highly significant difference between the two groups. Additionally, the p-value, significantly lower than the conventional significance level of 0.05, provides further evidence to reject the null hypothesis. These statistical findings strongly support the conclusion that a relationship exists between teachers' gender and their perceptions of the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum integration.

The implications of these results are noteworthy for educational policymakers, curriculum developers, and school administrators. Understanding the gender-based variations in teachers' perceptions can offer valuable insights into potential areas for improvement in curriculum implementation strategies. It highlights the importance of considering diverse perspectives and needs when designing and implementing educational initiatives. Moreover, addressing any disparities in perceptions between male and female teachers could contribute to fostering a more inclusive and supportive teaching environment, ultimately enhancing the quality of education provided to students.

Research Question 3

Is there a relationship between secondary school teachers' years of experience and their perception of integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana?

Hypothesis Testing

H_0 - There is no relationship between secondary school teachers' years of experience and their perception of integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana.

Table 3. ANOVA Test to Determine if There is a Relationship Exist Test Showing the Relationship between the Variables

ANOVA: Two-Factor Without Replication						
Source of Variation	S.S.	Df	M.S.	F	P-value	F crit
Years of Experience teaching the curriculum	105.3	29	3.631034	16.76497	1.11E-52	1.4955
Items	9.266666	14	0.6619	3.0561	0.000161	1.7161
Error	87.93333333	406	0.216585			
Total	202.5	449				

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) test results (Table 3) provides insight into the relationship between secondary school teachers' years of experience and their perception of integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower

Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana. The hypothesis under examination posits that there is no relationship between these variables. However, the ANOVA results reveal significant findings that challenge this hypothesis.

Firstly, the portion of the ANOVA table focusing on years of experience teaching the curriculum indicates a substantial effect. The high F-value of 16.76497, accompanied by an extremely low p-value of 1.11E-52, indicates a statistically significant relationship. This suggests that teachers' years of experience significantly influence their perception of curriculum integration. Moreover, comparing the F-value to the critical F-value reinforces this conclusion, as the former significantly exceeds the latter. Thus, the null hypothesis of no relationship between years of experience and perception is decisively rejected.

Additionally, the ANOVA results shed light on the impact of specific survey items on teachers' perceptions. The analysis shows that different survey items elicit varying responses from teachers, indicating the importance of item selection in accurately capturing teachers' perceptions. This is evidenced by the statistically significant F-value of 3.056103 and the corresponding low p-value of 0.000161. Consequently, the choice of survey items emerges as a critical factor influencing teachers' perceptions of curriculum integration.

Lastly, the error term in the ANOVA table accounts for unexplained variability in teachers' perceptions that cannot be attributed to either years of experience or specific survey items. While this variability exists, the significant effects of both years of experience and survey items underscore their importance in understanding teachers' perspectives on curriculum integration.

As such, the ANOVA results provide compelling evidence against the hypothesis that there is no relationship between secondary school teachers' years of experience and their perception of integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum. Both years of experience and the choice of survey items significantly impact teachers' perceptions, highlighting the need for nuanced consideration of these factors in educational policy and practice.

Discussion

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results indicated a statistically significant relationship between secondary school teachers' years of experience and their perceptions of integrating the consolidated mathematics curriculum. The findings suggest that teachers' perceptions of curriculum integration may evolve as they gain more experience in the classroom. Additionally, the choice and design of survey items play a crucial role in shaping teachers' perceptions, highlighting the importance of considering both years of experience and survey methodology when evaluating educators' attitudes toward curriculum integration.

These findings align with recent scholarly research in the field. A study by Rezat et al. (2021) investigated the factors influencing secondary mathematics teachers' perceptions of integrating technology into the curriculum. While their focus was not solely on a consolidated mathematics curriculum, their results suggest a similar trend, wherein teachers with more experience reported greater confidence and self-efficacy in integrating new approaches into the curriculum.

The t-test analysis (Table 2) reveals a statistically significant difference in the perceptions of integrating the Mathematics Consolidated Curriculum between male and female secondary school teachers in the Lower Corentyne District of Guyana. Male teachers exhibited a notably higher mean perception score compared to their female counterparts, indicating a gender-related discrepancy in how teachers perceive the effectiveness or adequacy of curriculum integration.

This finding aligns with contemporary research Van Zanten et al. (2021) and Blazar et al. (2021) examining gender differences in educational contexts. Rodriguez et al. (2020) and Ayuso et al. (2020) have explored gender disparities in various domains, including education, emphasising the importance of recognising and addressing such differences. Additionally, Perera et al. (2020) have examined how societal stereotypes and expectations can influence individuals' perceptions and behaviours, potentially contributing to gender-related discrepancies in educational settings.

However, it is crucial to note that the observed difference in perceptions does not necessarily imply superiority or inferiority on the part of either gender. Instead, it underscores the need for further investigation into the underlying factors contributing to these differences (Pak et al. 2020). Future research could explore how societal norms, personal experiences, and instructional approaches intersect with gender to shape teachers' perceptions of curriculum integration.

The highlighted aspects of the consolidated mathematics curriculum, such as relevance, student-centeredness, and adaptability, underscore the importance of these elements in promoting effective learning experiences. Recent scholars have echoed similar sentiments, emphasising the need for curricula that resonate with students' lives and promote critical thinking skills (Pak et al, 2020; Reis, 2018; Rezat et al., 2021)

Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, for instance, emphasises the significance of connecting learning to students' experiences to facilitate understanding and engagement (Mitchell, 2021). Moreover, contemporary researcher, Hattie (2023) stressed the importance of student-centred teaching in promoting deeper learning and critical thinking skills. Similarly, Rezat et al. (2021) and Senk and Thompson (2020) advocate for a curriculum that prioritises active engagement and problem-solving, aligning with the favourable views expressed by teachers regarding the effectiveness of the curriculum in enhancing students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Senk and Thompson (2020) work emphasises the importance of fostering a growth mindset and promoting mathematical thinking through hands-on, inquiry-based approaches.

However, concerns about the rigidity and abstractness of the curriculum resonate with discussions in the field of mathematics education. Joong and colleagues (2020) have highlighted the limitations of traditional, procedural approaches to teaching mathematics, emphasising the need for more flexible and conceptually oriented pedagogies. Additionally, Grimus (2020) emphasised the importance of adapting curriculum materials to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences, aligning with the need for further refinement identified by teachers.

Conclusion

The integration of the national consolidated mathematics curriculum in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana, has garnered substantial attention from educators, policymakers, and stakeholders. A systematic analysis of

secondary school teachers' perceptions offers valuable insights into the effectiveness and reception of this curriculum initiative.

The findings suggest a predominantly positive outlook among teachers, with a mean perception score of 2.87, indicating general agreement on the relevance of the curriculum to students' lives and its potential alignment with real-world applications. This aspect is crucial in fostering student engagement and understanding, a cornerstone of effective pedagogy.

However, certain concerns and disparities emerged amidst the positive reception. The t-test results unveiled a significant difference in perceptions between male and female teachers regarding curriculum integration, with a mean perception score of 6.50 for male teachers compared to 2.83 for female teachers. This discrepancy underscores the necessity of addressing gender-related factors in curriculum development and implementation strategies to ensure inclusivity and equitable educational outcomes.

Moreover, the ANOVA test results shed light on the influence of teachers' years of experience on their perceptions of curriculum integration. The statistically significant relationship between years of experience and perception, indicated by an F-value of 16.77 and an extremely low p-value of 1.11E-52, emphasises the importance of considering educators' professional backgrounds and expertise when gauging their views on educational initiatives. This finding highlights the need for tailored support and professional development programs to address educators' evolving needs and perspectives at different stages of their careers.

In light of these findings, it is evident that while the consolidated mathematics curriculum holds promise in enhancing mathematics education in the region, nuanced considerations and disparities must be addressed. Policymakers, curriculum developers, and education stakeholders must collaborate to refine the curriculum, address concerns regarding rigidity and abstractness, and provide adequate support and resources for teachers. By fostering a more inclusive and supportive teaching environment, policymakers can ensure that the curriculum meets the diverse needs of students and educators alike, ultimately enhancing the quality and effectiveness of mathematics education in the Lower Corentyne District of East Berbice Corentyne, Guyana.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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